

Nucleation Studies on Supersaturated Aqueous Solutions of Ammonium Dihydrogen Phosphate Doped with Ammonium and Potassium Sulfates

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Induction periods have been measured for various supersaturated aqueous solutions of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate doped with ammonium sulfate and potassium sulfate by the direct vision method. Various critical nucleation parameters have been calculated based on classical theory for homogeneous nucleation and discussed. The critical nucleation parameters increase with the increase in concentration of doping.

Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ((NH₄)H₂PO₄), ADP, is an interesting and useful material. ADP is isomorphous with KDP (potassium dihydrogen phosphate) and has tetragonal structure very similar to that of zircon. Also, it has the tetramolecular unit cell having the dimensions¹: $a = b = 7.510$ Å and $c = 7.564$ Å. ADP is soluble in water. Its solubilities at 20, 40, 60 and 80° are respectively 37.4, 56.7, 82.5 and 118.0 parts per 100 parts (w/w) of water². ADP is antiferroelectric and the Curie temperature T_c is 125° (not established definitely)³.

Nucleation process is the initial and important phenomenon in liquid-solid phase transition. The induction period (τ) can be measured^{4,5} and used to calculate certain nucleation parameters like interfacial tension (σ) of the solid relative to its solution, energy of formation (ΔG) of a critical nucleus, the radius of the nucleus (r) in equilibrium with its solution, etc. based on the classical theory for homogeneous nucleation. Nagalingam *et al.*^{6,7} made nucleation studies on aqueous ADP solutions with and without some added impurities. We report here the results of our nucleation studies (an attempt to investigate the effect of impurities added heavily and with both common and different ions on the nucleation parameters) on supersaturated aqueous solutions of ADP doped (impurity concentration in the range of 2000–10000 ppm) with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ separately (dotation given for the solution) in six different but definite ADP : dopant molecular ratios, viz. 1 : 0.000 (pure ADP), 1 : 0.002, 1 : 0.004, 1 : 0.006, 1 : 0.008 and 1 : 0.010. The critical nucleation parameters are calculated and the effect of supersaturation and concentration of doping on them is also discussed.

Results and Discussion

The results of measurements of τ and calculations of nucleation parameters are presented in Tables 1 and 2. For both the dopants ((NH₄)₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄), the value of τ decreases and hence the nucleation rate increases as the supersaturated concentration of the aqueous solution increases. Also, the induction period decreases with the increase in concentration of doping in the ADP solution. This

is similar to that observed⁸ for KDP doped with K₂CrO₄. It is observed that the values of ΔG and r decrease when the supersaturated concentration increases. This result is similar to that observed for pure and doped ADP^{6,7}, pure and doped KDP^{5,9-11} and FeSO₄·7H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O⁹.

TABLE 1—INDUCTION PERIODS AND NUCLEATION PARAMETERS OF PURE AND (NH₄)₂SO₄ DOPED ADP CRYSTALS

System	Supersaturation (x/x_0)	τ s	σ mJ m ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm	
ADP : (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (pure ADP)	1 : 0.000	1.30	1542	4.0141	6.08	0.77
	1.35	1164		4.64	0.67	
	1.40	878		3.69	0.60	
	1.45	574		3.03	0.54	
	1.50	508		2.54	0.50	
1 : 0.002	1.30	998	4.3374	7.67	0.83	
	1.35	828		5.86	0.73	
	1.40	614		4.66	0.65	
	1.45	355		3.82	0.59	
	1.50	250		3.21	0.54	
1 : 0.004	1.30	830	4.4418	8.24	0.85	
	1.35	615		6.29	0.74	
	1.40	480		5.01	0.66	
	1.45	325		4.19	0.60	
	1.50	225		3.45	0.55	
1 : 0.006	1.30	614	4.6430	9.41	0.89	
	1.35	500		7.19	0.78	
	1.40	386		5.72	0.69	
	1.45	274		4.69	0.63	
	1.50	165		3.94	0.58	
1 : 0.008	1.30	408	4.9124	11.14	0.94	
	1.35	355		8.52	0.82	
	1.40	282		6.77	0.73	
	1.45	209		5.55	0.66	
	1.50	102		4.66	0.61	
1 : 0.010	1.30	345	5.1712	13.00	0.99	
	1.35	260		9.93	0.87	
	1.40	198		7.90	0.77	
	1.45	132		6.48	0.70	
	1.50	75		5.44	0.64	

Saturated concentration, $x_0 = 2.498$ M.

At lower supersaturation levels the line plots (not shown) of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(x/x_0)$ are not linear (supposed to be linear as per the classical theory for homogeneous nucleation). Previous workers also observed a similar result

with their systems^{5,6,8-11}. Nagalingam *et al.*⁶ observed this non-linearity for pure ADP only at temperatures higher than 25°. However, linear relationship has been observed⁷ at 30° for ADP doped with NH₄Cl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, NH₄I, NH₄NO₃, KDP, and NaH₂PO₄ (doping concentration is only 100 ppm). As the doping concentration for (NH₄)₂SO₄ doped ADP in the present study ranges from 2000 to 10000 ppm and also the temperature is higher (32°), it is not logical to compare the result obtained by us with that obtained by Nagalingam *et al.*⁷ for (NH₄)₂SO₄ doped ADP.

TABLE 2—INDUCTION PERIODS AND NUCLEATION PARAMETERS OF PURE AND K₂SO₄ DOPED ADP CRYSTALS

System	Supersaturation (x/x_0)	τ s	σ mJm ⁻²	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	r nm	
ADP : (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	1 : 0.002	1.30	1135	4.2402	7.16	0.81
		1.35	850		5.47	0.71
		1.40	635		4.35	0.63
		1.45	450		3.57	0.57
		1.50	320		3.00	0.52
	1 : 0.004	1.30	820	4.4799	8.45	0.86
		1.35	610		6.46	0.75
		1.40	470		5.14	0.67
		1.45	345		4.21	0.61
		1.50	250		3.53	0.55
	1 : 0.006	1.30	580	4.6223	9.28	0.89
		1.35	455		7.09	0.78
		1.40	330		5.64	0.69
		1.45	240		4.63	0.63
		1.50	165		3.88	0.57
1 : 0.008	1.30	435	4.8282	10.58	0.93	
	1.35	350		8.08	0.81	
	1.40	260		6.43	0.72	
	1.45	185		5.27	0.65	
	1.50	118		4.44	0.60	
1 : 0.010	1.30	385	4.9723	11.56	0.96	
	1.35	290		8.83	0.89	
	1.40	200		7.02	0.74	
	1.45	122		5.76	0.67	
	1.50	60		4.84	0.62	

Saturated concentration, $x_0 = 2.498 M$

The deviations from the linear pattern do not arise from difficulties in the induction period measurements; the long induction periods at these lower supersaturations are more conveniently and accurately measured than at the higher supersaturations. A possible explanation is the occurrence of heterogeneous nucleation. However, from the available data on KDP with added impurities (concentrations of 2000–10000 ppm) it is understood that the solute impurities has less effect on this linear dependence. Though experiments are conducted under controlled conditions, crystal nucleation normally occurs earlier than expected, there being less time lag than classical theory for homogeneous nucleation would predict under the conditions. Shanmugham *et al.*⁵ reported that the main reason for this phenomenon is that there are normally between 10⁶ and 10⁸ unwanted impurity particles present per ml of aqueous solution, no matter whatever precautions are taken in performing the experiment. These particles are an aid to heterogeneous nucleation. So, the linear dependence of $\ln \tau$

on $1/\ln^2(x/x_0)$ may not be expected to observe in practice at lower supersaturation levels. Moreover, the effect of these unwanted impurity particles present in the aqueous solution is dominated over by the presence of more amount of solute in the higher supersaturated solutions. Hence, the linearity is expected to observe at higher supersaturations.

Considering the principles of homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation theories, the free energy of formation of a nucleus under heterogeneous nucleation is less than that of homogeneous conditions⁵.

Backiyam *et al.*⁹ observed less linear dependence with FeSO₄·7H₂O than with ZnSO₄·7H₂O. A qualitative explanation to this result can be attempted by considering the solubilities of these substances. The linear dependence is more when the solubility of the substance is more so that the substance molecule in the case of substance with higher solubility may dominate over the unwanted impurities present in the solvent in a better way than that in the case of substance with lower solubility.

The maximum practical limit for the measurement of induction period does not allow the supersaturation (x/x_0) to exceed 1.50. If the concentration is beyond the practical limit, then the nucleation occurs before the attainment of supersaturation (that is before cooling to the experimental temperature). This may also be due to the higher solubility of the substance. Hence, with these practical difficulties, the results obtained in the present study may be considered to be good.

It can be seen from the tables that the σ , ΔG and r values increase with the increase in concentration of doping in the ADP solution for both the dopants considered in the present study. This is similar to that observed for K₂CrO₄ doped KDP⁸.

Experimental

(NH₄)H₂PO₄, (NH₄)₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ (all AnalaR) and double-distilled water were used. Aqueous solutions of various supersaturated concentrations were prepared by dissolving the required amount of ADP and dopant at temperatures slightly higher than the saturation temperature. Supersaturation was obtained by natural cooling.

The experimental set-up for induction period (τ) measurement consisted of two identical nucleation cells (100 ml corning glass beakers) kept at a constant temperature of 32° (controlled to an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$). One of the cells was used as dummy (as insertion of thermometer in the experimental cell may disturb the system, this dummy cell was used for keeping the sensitive thermometer). Using a powerful lamp, the cells were illuminated. Supersaturated solutions of equal volume (25 ml) were taken in the cells at a higher temperature. A thermometer (accurate up to 0.1°) was placed in the dummy cell. As the temperature of the cell reached the experimental temperature, the time was noted. Once the nucleation occurred, it grew quickly and a bright sparkling particle was seen. The time of observation of the sparkling particle in the undisturbed nucleation cell

from the time at which the solution reaches the experimental temperature gave the induction period⁹.

Experiments were performed at selected degrees of supersaturations (x/x_0), viz. 1.30, 1.35, 1.40, 1.45 and 1.50, x being the mole fraction of solute in the supersaturated salt solution at the experimental temperature and x_0 the mole fraction of solute in the salt solution saturated at the experimental temperature. Several nucleation runs were carried out under controlled and unstirred conditions. Volume of the solution taken in the nucleation cell was maintained at 25 ml in all the experiments. Reproducible results with an accuracy of $\pm 2.3\%$ were obtained. Various critical nucleation parameters were calculated following the procedures adopted by Shanmugham *et al.*⁵ :

$$\sigma = RT [3m/(16\pi V^2 N)]^{1/3}$$

$$\Delta G = RTm/\ln^2(x/x_0)$$

$$r = 2\sigma V/[RT \ln(x/x_0)]$$

where, V , N , R , T and m are respectively the molar volume

of crystal, Avogadro's number, gas constant, temperature and slope of the line plot of $\ln \tau$ against $1/\ln^2(x/x_0)$.

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